

ISic0074

I.Sicily inscription 0074

Language

Punic

Type

dedication

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lilybaeum

Place of origin (modern)

Marsala

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Mozia, Villa Whittaker

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644809

Bibliography

Amadasi Guzzo, M.G. 1967. Le iscrizioni fenicie e puniche delle colonie in Occidente. Rome. At Sic.Pun.04

Whitaker, Joseph I. S. 1921. Motya, a Phoenician colony in Sicily. London. At 290 d fig.70

Salinas, A. 1871. Rassegna archeologica siciliana compilata da A. Salinas. Palermo. At 8

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